

Multi-source Time Series of Canopy Chlorophyll for Crops – Corn and Soybean Rotation

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Abstract: Monitoring canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) is essential for assessing crop photosynthetic function and productivity, yet characterizing its temporal variability remains a major challenge. This study aimed to generate a consistent, high-temporal-resolution CCab time series across seasons, crop types (corn and soybean), and years (2015–2024) by integrating *in situ* measurements with multispectral satellite imagery. CCab was derived using field data (leaf chlorophyll, leaf area index, and canopy reflectance) directly and as inputs to the Soil Canopy Observation Photosynthesis Energy (SCOPE) model. We produced dense CCab time series by combining field data with red-edge indices (CI705) from Harmonized Landsat/Sentinel (HLS) and Planet SuperDove (PSD) constellations. HLS CI705 was strongly correlated with PSD CI705 but outperformed it, yielding more consistent CCab estimates with lower uncertainty. Multi-sensor fusion using harmonized red-edge indices successfully captured fine-scale seasonal dynamics previously unattainable by a single sensor, and confirmed the transferability of CCab across crop types, seasons and multiple years. While promising for operational monitoring, the study highlights the critical need for continued advancements in cross-sensor calibration, radiometric harmonization and careful trending and comparison of multi-source red-edge indices and CCab product.

Keywords: chlorophyll; vegetation indices with red-edge bands; multispectral and hyperspectral reflectance; multi-source time series.

1 Introduction

Plant functional traits provide sensitive indicators of vegetation function and resilience (Larcher 2003). Chlorophyll (Cab) is central to the absorption of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and is closely linked to photosynthesis and crop productivity (Larcher 2003, Jones and Vaughan 2011). Leaf and canopy chlorophyll (LCab and CCab) vary with vegetation type, phenology, and environmental stress, producing measurable changes in spectral reflectance. These changes

can be quantified using vegetation indices, hyperspectral observations, and biophysical models (Houborg and Anderson 2009, Jones and Vaughan 2011, van der Tol et al. 2009, 2014, Knyazikhin et al. 2013). Despite these advances, uncertainties in CCab estimation persist, mainly due to limited characterization of temporal variability. Dense chlorophyll time series are required to capture seasonal dynamics and short-term stress responses (Chadwick et al. 2025), yet no single sensor meets the spatial, spectral, and temporal requirements for such monitoring. As a result, integrating multispectral and hyperspectral data from multiple platforms—such as Harmonized Landsat-8/9 and Sentinel-2A/B (Claverie et al. 2018), PlanetScope SuperDove (PSD) with hyperspectral proximal and spaceborne - has emerged as a promising approach to generate consistent CCab datasets across scales. Vegetation indices (VIs) using red-edge bands are particularly effective for CCab estimation. Gitelson et al. (Gitelson and Merzlyak 2003, Gitelson and Peng 2012) showed that when a red-edge band near 705 nm is available, CI705 and red-edge NDVI are strongly sensitive to CCab but among the least sensitive to crop differences. However, while spectral VIs can be transferable across crop type, inter-comparison of derived CCab remains challenging due to differences in spectral and spatial resolution, sensor characteristics, calibration data, and viewing geometry (Gitelson and Peng 2012, Peng et al. 2017, Zhou et al. 2026). Although transferability across sites and crops has been demonstrated at Landsat scale (Peng et al. 2017), further evaluation across sensors, vegetation seasonality and environmental conditions is needed. The objective of this study was to generate high-temporal-resolution, multi-sensor CCab time series through the integration of field measurements with hyperspectral and multispectral data. Specifically, the study aimed to develop methods to ensure consistent scaling of CCab across seasons, crop types, and years by linking multispectral imagery incorporating red-edge bands at very high (3 m) and medium (30 m) spatial resolutions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

Data were collected from 2015–2024 at the Optimizing Production Inputs for Economic and Environmental Enhancement (OPE3) site at the Beltsville Agricultural Research Center (BARC), MD, USA (39.030686, -76.84546, 50 m asl), operated by the USDA Agricultural Research Service. The 22-ha field is part of the Long-Term Agroecosystem Research (LTAR) network and includes a 10 m eddy covariance tower. Corn (*Zea mays L.*) and soybean (*Glycine max (L.) Merr.*) are grown annually on predominantly sandy loam soils under rainfed conditions and optimal nitrogen fertilization. The region has a warm temperate climate with hot, humid summers and mild winters, producing strong seasonal variability in crop leaf area index (LAI) and canopy chlorophyll.

2.2 Field measurements of chlorophyll (Cab) and proximal reflectance

From 2015–2024 (excluding 2023), leaf chlorophyll (LCab), canopy closure, and LAI were measured multiple times per season using a LAI-2200 plant canopy analyzer (Li-Cor). Leaf samples from the sunlit upper canopy were analyzed for LCab ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) using standard DMSO extraction and spectrophotometry (Wellburn, 1994). Fresh and dry weights were also recorded (Lhotáková et al. 2025), recording fresh and dry weights [5,13]. Canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) was calculated as:

$$\text{CCab} = \text{LCab} * \text{LAI}. \quad (1)$$

Canopy reflectance was measured using multiple approaches. In 2017, 2018, and 2024, high-frequency proximal reflectance was collected with an automated FLoX system (Julitta et al. 2017), acquiring downwelling and nadir-viewing upwelling radiance from 1 m above the canopy, at ~2 min intervals, over 350–1100 nm (1 nm resolution). Data were filtered and aggregated to midday reflectance (12:00 ±1 h) and used in modeling and to derive vegetation indices (Julitta et al. 2017, Campbell et al. 2019). In 2019, reflectance was measured at mid-day along transects using an ASD FieldSpec 3 spectrometer (400–2400 nm) with a Spectralon reference panel. Measurements were taken at nadir, 20–30 cm above the canopy (Campbell et al. 2019).

2.3 Space-borne image data

We used the HLS data (Claverie et al. 2018), combining Landsat 8/9 and Sentinel-2A/B with consistent atmospheric correction, BRDF normalization, and applied cloud and shadow masking to retain only high-quality pixels. PlanetScope SuperDove (PSD) imagery (3 m resolution) includes eight spectral bands. We used PSD harmonized data, which includes six VNIR bands harmonized to Sentinel-2 plus blue and red-edge 705 nm bands, all orthorectified and atmospherically corrected to ensure temporal consistency and to minimize uncertainty in spectral response across time and location. DLR Earth Sensing Imaging Spectrometer (DESI) hyperspectral imagery (L2A surface reflectance) was obtained via TCloud, providing 187 VNIR bands (2.5 nm spectral, 30 m spatial

resolution) (DESI ATBD 2015, Campbell et al. 2022). Images were selected based on cloud-free conditions, $\leq 20^\circ$ off-nadir viewing, and acquisition within ± 1 h of local noon.

2.4 Retrieval of CCab using a biophysical model

Using SCOPE v1.73, we used in an inversion the canopy radiative transfer module (RTMo) with the measured reflectance and leaf traits to generate dense time series of LCab, LAI, and CCab (van der Tol et al. 2009, van der Tol et al. 2014). Trait estimates were optimized by maximizing R^2 and minimizing RMSE between observed and simulated reflectance, retaining only retrievals with $\text{RMSE} \leq 0.02$ for VI calibration to CCab. Using SCOPE v1.73, the canopy radiative transfer module (RTMo) was inverted with measured reflectance (from FLoX, ASD and DESI) to generate time series of LCab, LAI, and CCab. Model performance was evaluated by maximizing R^2 and minimizing RMSE between observed and simulated reflectance, only retrievals with $\text{RMSE} \leq 0.02$ were retained.

2.5 Vegetation indices sensitive to CCab

Twenty-four vegetation indices sensitive to CCab (Vegetation Indices 2026) were calculated (Gitelson and Peng 2012, Peng et al. 2017, Zhou et al. 2026). Indices incorporating red-edge bands (e.g., CI705, red-edge NDVI) were of specific interest, as they are suggested to have reduced sensitivity to crop type. The space-borne data available for OPE3 for 2015–2024 period were assembled, stored, filtered and processed to VIs on the NASA-GSFC ADAPT cluster. We located the OPE3 study site on the images and collected reflectance spectra and VIs from 60–100 m diameter area for all dates for analysis. The proximal and PSD bands and VIs were normalized radiometrically to the HLS 30 m data, to obtain consistent multisource algorithms for CCab characterization. Using high and medium (30 m and 3 m) resolution data we tested whether the CCab to VI relationships are transferable among sensors, crop type and across seasons.

3 Results

3.1 Field measurements and dense time-series of CCab

Field measurements showed strong seasonal variability in CCab for both corn and soybean (Figure 1). CCab exhibited a clear seasonal pattern, with significantly higher values during mid-season and lower values in spring and autumn. The differences in CCab between crop types were not statistically significant. Across the study period, maximum CCab reached $200 \pm 25 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, observed for soybean at mid-2021. For both crops, lower peak values were recorded in 2015–2016, 2018–2019, and 2022–2024. Spring and autumn measurements were consistently lower, reflecting early growth and senescence stages, however, these values were highly sensitive to sampling date and were essential for capturing the full seasonal range of CCab.

To obtain temporally dense CCab estimates and better characterize seasonal dynamics (Figures 3 and 4), proximal VNIR reflectance measurements were combined with field data and used to invert the SCOPE RTMo.

Figure 1. Canopy chlorophyll ($CCab = LCab * LAI$) measured at OPE3 during the 2015-2024 timeframe (plotted are means and standard deviations).

The inversion produced consistent, high-temporal-resolution $CCab$ retrievals across all seasons and provided additional training data for satellite-based $CCab$ models using HLS and PSD CI705. The resulting linear relationship between $CCab$ and CI705 captured the seasonal variability effectively.

A strong linear relationship was observed between vegetation indices derived from HLS and PSD data, as well as between $CCab$ retrieved from HLS (S30) and PSD datasets (Figures 2 and 3). However, PSD CI705 exhibited higher variability than HLS-based estimates (Figure 2). Correspondingly, PSD-based $CCab$ showed greater standard deviation and a tendency to overestimate high $CCab$ values, indicating higher uncertainty at upper chlorophyll levels. Overall, $CCab$ values across datasets ranged from approximately 20 to 215 $\mu g\ cm^{-2}$ (Figures 3 and 4).

Seasonal dynamics were consistent across years: crops were planted in May, followed by a rapid increase in $CCab$ from May to July, reaching peak values in early August. Senescence began thereafter, with $CCab$ steadily declining through November (Figure 4). These detailed seasonal patterns are critical for developing robust, transferable $CCab$ retrieval algorithms across seasons and crop types.

3.2 Linking VIs and $CCab$ from multiple sensors

Frequently, reflectance VIs saturate early in the growing season and the relationships to canopy traits based on these VIs may not be transferable across the seasons. For

seasonal scaling using VIs a linear relationship with $CCab$ is required. To enable seasonal scaling, we evaluated linear relationships between VIs and $CCab$ using regression analysis, with model performance assessed via the coefficient of determination (R^2), which provide information on the explained variation in $CCab$. The analysis established linear relationships and strong correlations for many of the VIs sensitive to $CCab$, from which CI705 exhibited strongest correlation to $CCab$ (Figure 3) using data from all seasons and sensors (Figure 4). The HLS S30 CI705 outperformed the PSD index. The reduced performance and higher variability in PSD-based estimates are likely due to residual radiometric inconsistencies across the satellite constellation, differences in viewing geometry, higher spatial resolution effects, and remaining uncertainties not fully mitigated by the harmonization process.

The HLS dataset provided a radiometrically consistent 30 m reference for calibration and harmonization of PlanetScope (PSD) bands and VIs. Using field, proximal, and satellite observations (HLS S30 and PSD), we generated a continuous $CCab$ time series for OPE3 covering 2015–2024. Mean $CCab$ values (± 1 standard deviation) are shown by the acquisition date in Figure 4.

Since the high variability in the PSD $CCab$ is evident at the peak of the 2023-2024 growing seasons, when there were no significant canopy changes, this is likely due to differences in the PSD observation geometry and/or instruments intercalibration. The field $CCab$ (Figure 4, yellow) provided baseline values for the SCOPE/RTMo

Figure 2. Correlation between CI705 vegetation index ($CI705 = Rn / R705 - 1$) derived using HLS and PSD data by matching same day satellite observations (plotted means and standard deviations).

Figure 3. Canopy chlorophyll ($CCab$) derived using HLS vs. Planet SD data, matching same day satellite observations (plotted are means and standard deviations).

Figure 4. Canopy chlorophyll (CCab) time series derived using Field CCab measurements (yellow), Red-edge index CI705 from Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel (HLS S30, black), Planet Super Dove (PSD, green), and Reflectance spectra from DLR Earth Sensing Imaging Spectrometer collected (DESIS, pink), proximal FloX (red) and ASD (blue). Plotted are CCab means (± 1 StDev.) per date. The very dense CCab data (red) obtained with spectral reflectance and biophysical model (i.e., SCOPE/RTMo) were used to train linear models to derive CCab with the HLS S30 and PSD CI705 vegetation index, where $CCab = (39.70 * CI705 - 0.99)$.

inversion and served for a partial confirmation of the CCab satellite estimates for OPE3.

To quantify the differences in CCab between the HLS and PSD time series, we computed $\Delta CCab$ (Figure 5), where:

$$\Delta CCab = CCab(HLS) - CCab(PSD). \quad (2)$$

PSD-derived CCab showed greater variability around the mean compared to HLS. $\Delta CCab$ indicated PSD underestimation during late 2020–2021 and overestimation during most of the remaining period, with the largest positive bias in late 2022. The difference between the HLS and PSD standard deviations further confirmed higher uncertainty in PSD estimates, particularly during 2021–2022.

4 Discussion

This study evaluated the transferability of canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) estimates based on the red-edge vegetation index CI705 across multiple sensors and seasons in a corn–soybean system at OPE3. By integrating field measurements, proximal observations, and multi-sensor satellite data, we produced a high-frequency CCab time series at medium spatial resolution spanning 2015–2024.

Figure 5. Differences in CCab, derived by subtracting CCab PSD from CCab HLS (means and standard errors).

Our results demonstrate that CI705 derived from the Harmonized Landsat Sentinel (HLS) dataset consistently outperformed PlanetScope (PSD) equivalents, yielding more stable CCab estimates with lower uncertainty (Figure 3–5). This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that red-edge indices are among the most reliable proxies for chlorophyll retrieval due to their sensitivity to chlorophyll absorption and reduced saturation compared to traditional visible/near-infrared indices (e.g., NDVI) (Gitelson et al. 2003, Gitelson and Peng 2012). However, their performance remains strongly dependent on sensor spectral fidelity and calibration consistency. The observed differences between HLS- and PSD-derived CI705 likely reflect a combination of residual radiometric inconsistencies within the PlanetScope constellation, differences in viewing geometry, and the effects of higher spatial resolution, which increases sensitivity to sub-pixel heterogeneity. These factors are known to introduce uncertainty in cross-sensor harmonization, particularly when radiometric normalization does not fully account for directional effects and sensor-to-sensor variability (Pahlevan et al. 2019, Claverie et al. 2018).

Importantly, the multi-source fusion approach enabled detection of a wider CCab dynamic range and finer temporal variability than any single dataset alone (Figure 3 and 4). This is consistent with prior work showing that combining multispectral and hyperspectral observations can enhance sensitivity to phenological transitions and short-term stress responses by mitigating temporal sparsity and individual sensor limitations (Knyazikhin et al. 2013, Asner and Martin 2008). The resulting dense CCab time series improves the ability to resolve finer canopy changes, which is critical for early stress detection and monitoring crop development dynamics.

Overall, CI705 proved to be a robust and transferable indicator of CCab across corn and soybean canopies, multiple seasons, and multiple sensor configurations. This supports previous findings that red-edge-based indices

can provide stable chlorophyll estimates across vegetation types when properly harmonized (Delegido et al. 2011, Gitelson et al. 2015). However, transferability is conditional on consistent radiometric calibration and appropriate handling of spatial and directional effects.

A key prerequisite for reliable upscaling of CCab is the spectral and spatial homogeneity of the calibration dataset and the observed canopy. Variability in canopy structure, background soil influence, and vertical leaf distribution can introduce scale-dependent biases in reflectance–chlorophyll relationships. These effects highlight the importance of integrating field measurements and radiative transfer modeling, such as SCOPE, to constrain biophysical variability and improve the physical interpretability of empirical VI relationships.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that multi-sensor data fusion using harmonized red-edge indices can produce consistent, high-temporal-resolution time series that effectively scale CCab across growing seasons, crop rotations and years. While CI705 provides a strong and transferable chlorophyll proxy, sensor-specific uncertainties remain a critical consideration, particularly when using data from commercial constellations comprised of numerous satellite sensors of different ages. Continued improvements in cross-sensor calibration, radiometric harmonization and careful trending of red-edge vegetation indices from multi-satellite constellations will be essential for the operational deployment of multi-source vegetation CCab monitoring systems.

Future research will evaluate the transferability of the approach to deciduous and boreal forests, prairie grasslands and tundra ecosystems across the United States, for which very dense reflectance time series are being assembled.

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